

Establishment of rainfed winter crops under different N fertilizer and tillage treatments after wet rice, West Bengal, India, 1989-90.^a

Treatment	Seedlings (no./m ²)	Branches (no./plant)	Grains (no./panicle or pod)	1,000-seed wt(g)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Straw yield (t/ha)	Net return (\$/ha)
<i>Crops</i>							
Lentil	115	9.5	1.6	17.0	0.73	2.71	361
Grasspea	85	7.4	2.4	62.9	1.40	2.83	518
Mustard	303	3.2	2.8	2.1	0.33	1.04	284
Wheat	115	136.7	24.3	37.9	1.30	2.21	249
Beans	28	4.7	2.6	85.7	0.59	2.30	331
Mean	129	32.3	6.8	41.2	0.84	2.23	320
LSD (0.05)	22	5.2	6.7	9.8	0.95	1.04	
<i>N level (kg/ha)</i>							
0	131	27.6	5.7	38.6	0.73	2.00	281
50	127	31.0	7.8	43.9	0.95	2.46	360
Mean	129	32.3	6.8	41.2	0.84	2.23	320
LSD (0.05)	ns	5.1	1.2	5.1	0.07	0.31	
<i>Tillage number</i>							
0	128	33.8	7.6	40.8	0.88	0.63	382
4	130	30.8	5.9	41.6	0.79	1.82	259
Mean	129	32.3	6.8	41.2	0.84	2.23	320
LSD (0.05)	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	0.37	-

^a Basic IR36 rice yielded 4.1 t/ha with net return of US\$507/ha.

IR36 rice was transplanted 20 Jul 1989, 21 d after seeding, at 25- × 25-cm spacing with 4 seedlings/hill. We applied 60-30-30 kg NPK/ha at planting. The crop was harvested on 31 Oct.

Lentil (*Lens culinaris*, cv. L-9-12), grasspea (*Lathyrus sativas*, cv. Nirmal),

mustard (*Brassica campestris*, cv. RW351), wheat (*Triticum aestivum*, cv. UP262), and beans (*Phaseolus vulgaris*, cv. PDR14) were broadcast seeded over the rice crop 1 d before harvest under zero tillage (ZT) conditions. The same crops were also broadcast seeded on 30

Nov after conventional tillage (4 times) with bullocks (CT). Seeding rate in kilograms/hectare was 20 for lentil, 30 for grasspea, 6 for mustard, 100 for wheat, and 50 for beans. We broadcast no N or 50 kg N/ha as per treatment 1 d after harvest in ZT and at plowing in CT. With ZT, lentil was harvested on 3 Feb 1990, grasspea on 1 Feb, mustard on 27 Jan, wheat on 7 Feb, and beans on 2 Feb. With CT they were harvested on 15 Feb, 10 Feb, 27 Jan, 7 Feb, and 11 Feb, respectively.

Rainfed winter crops can be established in rice fallows, although yields differ significantly among crops. Grasspea (grain and stover) yielded more than the other crops (see table).

After transplanting irrigated rice, rainfed winter crops yielded more grain and stover under ZT than under CT (see table) because of higher soil moisture and longer growing period. Winter crop grain and straw yields responded significantly to 50 kg N/ha. Grasspea had the highest net return, followed by lentil and beans. N fertilization gave higher net returns than the control, as did ZT compared with CT (see table).

Integrated pest management—diseases

A trap plant method to predict the occurrence of rice blast (BI)

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B1 caused by *Pyricularia oryzae* Cav. is a serious rice production constraint. Rice straw and seeds and weeds are primary sources of infection.

Managing B1 requires a forecasting system in which weather conditions and aerial spore densities are monitored. We used trap plants in a ricefield to estimate the spore population during Jan 1990-Mar 1991 in Amphoe Seinoi, Noonthaburi Province. Rice variety RD23, which is highly susceptible to B1, was planted in five seedling boxes (5 × 10 cm). We placed 7-d-old RD23 seedlings in the field for 2-3 d and then brought them into a

greenhouse. Conspicuous leaf B1 lesions were counted on each plant about 5 d later. We stuck slides coated with gelatin to the lesions to estimate spore production.

On 31 Jan 1991, we observed 100 infected trap plants, each with an average of 5 lesions and a mean sporulation of 110 spores/lesion (see figure). We advised farmers to spray tricyclazole 75% wettable powder in the neighboring fields.

At the booting stage (19 Feb), 80 infected trap plants had a mean sporulation of 80 spores/lesion. We issued the same recommendation to farmers.

By the panicle growth stage (22 Feb), the lesions/plant, spores/lesion, and diseased trap plants were reduced (see figure). By applying the treatment, farmers obtained a high grain yield (6.7 t/ha) with a net return of about US\$950.

These results suggest that trap plants can be used to predict the occurrence of B1. Rice trap plants should be placed in

ricefields 2 wk before sowing and then at 30, 55, 65, and 75 d after sowing to monitor disease progress. □

Population of *P. oryzae* and leaf blast incidence at different rice growth stages. DI = disease incidence.

Surveys of disease or insect incidence/severity in one environment are useful only if the information is related to other variables (e.g., climatic factors, crop intensification, cultivars, management practices, etc.). By itself, information on incidence in one environment does not increase scientific knowledge.